

A LITERATURE REVIEW ON BURNOUT WITHIN THE ASIAN DEMOGRAPHIC

by

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Abstract

Gaining insight into burnout and its fundamental causes is essential for universities and corporations seeking to enhance their support for students and employees. A significant gap exists in our comprehension of burnout within the Asian American community, particularly within educational and workplace environments. We aim to bridge this gap by conducting a comprehensive literature review to uncover shared patterns in the characterization of burnout and its origins within the Asian population, both in the USA and abroad. Burnout is a multifaceted issue that could be influenced by various factors, including biological, psychological, and sociological factors. These influences can fluctuate among different populations and contexts. Surveys such as the Maslach Burnout Inventory, Copenhagen Burnout Inventory, and Oldenburg Burnout Inventory are frequently employed to assess burnout. These tools share a common element: exhaustion, which, in the context of burnout, signifies feelings of being drained, unable to cope, fatigued, and lacking energy. Our research delves into the origins and consequences of burnout within the Asian population and explores potential strategies to alleviate burnout within this demographic, considering biological, psychological, socioeconomic, and cultural aspects. We suggest that universities can play a pivotal role in supporting Asian American students, contributing to the prevention of and recovery from burnout by drawing from practical approaches employed in higher education and workplace settings.

Introduction

Who experiences burnout:

Burnout is common within various demographics (Lawrence et al., 2022) and can happen at different life stages, including primary education and secondary education such as in Korean middle and high schoolers revealing perfectionistic traits among academic burnout (Chang et al., 2015), undergraduate education viewed through Filipino college students examining personality, academic motivation and burnout (David, 2010), higher educationn showcased Indian medical students relationship between resilience and experiences of burnout (Pharasi et al., 2020), and the workforce exemplified by Vietnamese nurses on the impacts of violence and burnout (Do et al., 2023). While burnout is a prevalent concern throughout different demographics, I focused on articles addressing burnout in the Asian population. To gain a more comprehensive understanding of burnout in the Asian demographic. This allowed me to explore the causes and impacts of burnout within the Asian demographic at large and to identify potential strategies for reducing burnout. These possible solutions identified within the broader Asian demographic could be applied to address burnout within the Asian American population.

How is burnout measured and defined:

The lowest consensus of burnout across most of the papers is that burnout deals with exhaustion. Exhaustion, in the context of burnout, signifies feelings of being overextended (Listopad, 2021). The feeling of being overextended can mean that a person is feeling overwhelmed and stressed. Burnout is measured in various ways via inventories and interviews. An inventory is a list of items, often in question form, used in describing and studying behavior, interests, and attitudes (American Psychological Association, 2018). The most common inventories found within the articles studied include the Maslach Burnout Inventory (MBI),

Copenhagen Burnout Inventory (CBI), and Oldenburg Burnout Inventory (OLBI). In the MBI, key aspects of burnout included increased feelings of emotional exhaustion, the development of negative and cynical attitudes, and the tendency to evaluate oneself negatively (Maslach et al., 1981). In the CBI, the core of burnout is fatigue and exhaustion (Kristensen et al., 2005). The 16-item OLBI evaluates the fundamental aspects of burnout: exhaustion and disengagement (Demerouti, 1999). According to OLBI, exhaustion is described as the outcome of intense physical, emotional, and cognitive stress resulting from prolonged exposure to specific job demands over time (Demerouti, 1999). Other burnout inventories are less commonly used, such as the Pines' Burnout Measure (BM), Psychologist Burnout Inventory (PBI), or even the Burnout Assessment Tool (BAT), which focuses on exhaustion and various other aspects such as mental distance, cognitive impairment, and emotional impairment.

Methods:

To investigate burnout within the Asian demographic, I completed a literature review. Originally, my proposal centered on research regarding burnout among Filipino American undergraduates, encompassing 14 original articles concentrating on burnout within the Filipino and Filipino American communities. My Google Scholar searches involved the terms "burnout" or "treatments of burnout" paired with one of these terms: "Filipino," "Filipino American," and "undergraduate." As the research progressed, I shifted my focus to a broader literature review on burnout within the Asian demographic. Utilizing the initial 14 articles, I examined Google Scholar "cited by #" feature to identify additional papers referencing each article. Subsequently, I expanded my Google Scholar search, adding keywords "Vietnamese," "Chinese," "Korean," "Japanese," and "Indian." I used these specific key terms because these populations are what was

shown as overrepresented in the United States 2021 census data (Rico et al. 2023). I continued to explore the “cited by #” for relevance to burnout causes, impacts, or treatments. In total, I reviewed 77 articles related to burnout. To understand burnout’s definition and measurement and to determine the scope, I examined 23 articles broadly, mainly focusing on burnout inventory measurements such as MBI, CBI, OLBI, etc. Subsequently, I narrowed my focus to 16 articles specifically studying burnout within Asian demographics in universities and the workplace, highlighting causes, impacts, and support mechanisms for burnout.

Figure 1. Roadmap of Articles focused on Burnout.

A total of 78 articles were examined in this literature review, exploring various life stages of burnout such as primary and secondary education (5), undergraduate university (28), higher education (9), and workforce (29) as well as variations in how it's assessed by inventories

including MBI (44), CBI (7), OLBI (8), and others (19) in individuals. Subsequently, the focus narrowed down to 28 articles specifically addressing Asian populations, who are overrepresented in the 2021 United States census data. This subset of research focused on burnout among university students (9) and those in the workforce (12).

Results

Causes of Burnout

Some factors that can cause burnout in general can be biological, psychological, or socioeconomic (Listopad, 2021). Examples of factors that can affect burnout fall within ten categories: (1) lifestyle, (2) physical and mental health, (3) self-reference, (4) relaxation, (5) work-to-life interrelation, (6) support, (7) working environment, (8) Big Five personality traits, (9) perceived meaningfulness and (10) sense of homeliness (Listopad, 2021). Within the Asian demographic, similarities in the causes of burnout included support, working environment, and sense of homeliness.

Individuals who receive support from their personal and professional circles tend to experience less burnout than those with less support (Listopad, 2021). The working environment represents another influential factor impacting burnout, comprising elements like workload over time, control over tasks, and the overall psychosocial climate (Listopad, 2021). When individuals face a heavier workload, longer hours, lack of control over their tasks, or a negative relationship with management, there is an increased risk of burnout (Listopad, 2021). The aspect of a sense of homeliness has been associated with burnout, encompassing factors such as a sense of community, alignment of personal values with organizational values, and the balance between effort and rewards (Listopad, 2021). When an individual lacks a sense of community, feels

disconnected from their work motivations, or experiences low job security and lack of respect, they can be at a higher risk of burnout (Listopad, 2021).

There can also be socio-cultural factors that can be a difference between non-Western and Western cultures regarding the cause of burnout (Savicki, 2002). When examining different cultures, factors influencing burnout were found to include individualism versus collectivism, prioritization of career success (“masculinity”) versus quality of life (“femininity”), power distance, and uncertainty avoidance (Savicki, 2002). Burnout was shown to be more prevalent in countries where people are uncomfortable with uncertainty, accept unequal power distribution, and prioritize career success over quality of life (Schaufeli, 2017).

As an Asian American, my original focus was understanding burnout within the Asian American population. However, with limitations in the literature on Asian Americans and burnout, the scope of the literature review has been widened to the Asian demographic to better understand the relationship and potential methods to prevent burnout. Some causes found within the articles were similar to those of other demographics, such as lack of support, poor working environment, and an absence of a sense of homeliness. Within higher education, there was an article on burnout among Filipino college students in which there was a lack of homeliness, and students were affected by the disapproval of others, causing burnout (Ramos, 2016). Within Vietnamese university students, there was a lack of support and a lack of homeliness, which caused burnout due to the isolation caused by COVID-19 (Tran, 2019). Within the workforce, particularly in nursing, in each Asian ethnicity burnout is commonly attributed to various factors, encompassing structural and personal elements. Structural factors like inadequate salaries, staffing shortages, demanding work conditions, and personal issues such as inequitable rewards and insufficient support contribute to burnout. For instance, within the Filipino nursing

community, burnout is influenced by factors such as lower salaries, insufficient staffing levels, and overwhelming workloads (Alibudbud, 2023). Similarly, among Vietnamese nurses, exhaustion stemming from heavy workloads and feelings of unfairness, like lack of recognition and appreciation, are prevalent (Nguyen, 2018). In addition, in the Japanese nursing demographic, workload, and interpersonal conflicts, such as lack of supervisor and coworker support, are major contributors to burnout (Kitaoka-Higashiguchi, 2005). Similarly, in the Korean nursing demographic, burnout can be influenced by experience in the current department, overtime, shift type, depression, job stress, emotional labor, clinical experience, reduced resilience, and the perceived threat of coronavirus disease 2019 (Cha et al., 2023). In Kar's study of nurses in India, nurses experienced burnout as a result of role conflicts, role ambiguity, intensive workload, work-home conflict, shifts in work attitudes, job complexity, physical environment, and organizational politics (Kar, 2014).

Some factors involved in burnout seemed to differ in the Asian demographic in comparison to other cultures around the world, such as perfectionism, internet addiction within higher education, and violence within the workforce (Chang et al., 2016; Do et al. 2023; Gu et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2019; Tomaszek et al., 2022; Yoon et al., 2016; Zhang et al., 2007). For example, among Korean university students, maladaptive perfectionism was positively related to amotivation and lack of meaning to a task, leading to academic burnout (Chang, 2016). Chinese university students who had perceived expectations from parents leading to perfectionism, experienced doubts in their actions and had and experienced more burnout (Zhang, 2007). Internet addiction after COVID19 was also shown to be associated with academic stress and exhaustion, leading to burnout among Chinese university students (Gu, 2023). Similarly, phubing, which refers to ignoring those around an individual in favor of a mobile device, led to

reduced engagement and satisfaction among Japanese university students, and was positively associated with burnout (Tomaszek, 2022). The impact of phubing was in part evidenced by students' negative perceptions of peers and teachers, declining motivation for academic endeavors, and a perception of lessons as lacking meaning and significance (Tomaszek, 2022). Within the workforce, violence impacted burnout among the Asian demographic. For example, among Korean nurses, burnout was linked to experiences of abuse and violence in the workplace (Yoon, 2016). Among nurses in Vietnam who work in public hospitals, violence, mainly verbal abuse, affected work stress, reduced job satisfaction and work efficiency/performance, and was associated with signs of stress/depression or intending to change jobs/reposition of work (Do et al. 2023). There was also another study on workplace violence affecting burnout within nurses in China, as violence was found to be associated with higher incidences of burnout, less job satisfaction, lower patient safety, and more adverse events (Liu et al., 2019).

Impacts of Burnout

Impacts among Asian students experiencing burnout can include dropping out of school, both physical and mental exhaustion, mental health conditions like anxiety and depression, as well as sentiments of hopelessness and cynicism (Chang et al. 2016; Gu et al., 2023; Ramos et al., 2021; Reyes et al., 2016; Schaufeli et al., 2002; Tomaszek et al., 2022; Tran et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2007). At the same time, impacts among Asian populations within the workforce can include resignations, change of profession, distress, fatigue, and mental health disorders such as anxiety (Alibudbud, 2023; Cha et al., 2023; Do et al., 2023; Kar et al., 2014; Kitaoka-Higashiguchi, 2005; Liao et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2018; Yoon et al., 2016).

Guidance for Reducing Burnout

Approaches from the literature review within both academic and workforce settings underscore the importance of early interventions, fostering social support, and promoting intrinsic motivation. Reyes and Tran highlight the importance of social support, particularly within Filipino and Vietnamese college students respectively (Reyes et al. 2016 and Tran, 2019). Ramos emphasizes the role of social support alongside resilience in mediating burnout, emphasizing adaptation to college life as influenced by personality, social support systems, and life satisfaction, all of which contribute to promoting mental health (Ramos, 2016). Liao underscores the importance of social support, particularly within Chinese working contexts (Liao et al. 2022). These insights collectively advocate for multifaceted approaches that address both individual and social factors to alleviate burnout among Asian students.

Conclusion:

Prevention of Burnout within Asian American University Students

As a current Asian American university student who works part-time on campus, I believe that fostering and cultivating a student's intrinsic motivation and social support within the workplace and in the classroom are more effective ways of reducing burnout than advocating for mental health programs and campus resources. This is because learning about available programs and resources only sometimes translates to using these resources due to both scheduling conflicts and stigma. However, being surrounded by others who understand our lived experience and remind us to focus on our overall goals can help motivate us and build confidence to avoid or move through burnout.

Next Steps

Currently, there is not much data found about burnout in the Asian American student demographic, so potential future work can include designing surveys specifically for this population and interviewing Asian American undergraduate students to investigate more on the causes and impacts of burnout. Future studies can focus on specific Asian American populations, such as Filipino Americans. It would also be interesting to compare causes, impacts, and potential solutions regarding burnout across ethnicities and countries to determine how cultural influence may impact burnout.

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